

Measurement, Analysis and Estimation of the Noise Figure of an AGC Amplifier

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Article History:

Received: 21.02.2025 Revised: 12.03.2025 Accepted: 17.03.2025 Published: 25.03.2025

ABSTRACT:

The front end of a radio receiver contains an AGC amplifier so as to maintain the specified performance over a wide input dynamic range of the receiver. The carrier to noise ratio or the bit energy to noise density ratio at the demodulator input is directly proportional to the noise figure of its front-end AGC amplifier. Hence, it is important to estimate the noise figure of an AGC amplifier over its input dynamic range or AGC range while designing such radio reception systems. The paper describes an analytical method to estimate the noise figure of an AGC amplifier and also an experimental method (called the gain method) to measure its noise figure practically. Using the analytical method, the noise figures of a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier have been estimated. The comparison between the estimated values and the measured values is also presented in the paper.

Keywords: Automatic Gain Control (AGC), Bit Error Rate (BER), Fixed Gain Amplifier (FGA), Input Dynamic Range (IDR), Noise Figure (NF), Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR), Voltage Variable Attenuator (VVA).

Suggested Citation: P. Gupta, A.H. Syed, M.T. Wara, Y. Krupa, T. Esha, "Measurement, Analysis and Estimation of the Noise Figure of an AGC Amplifier," *Eur. J. Appl. Sc. Eng. Technol.*, vol. 3(2), pp. 215-224, Mar-Apr 2025. DOI: 10.59324/ejaset.2025.3(2).18

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INTRODUCTION

For a digital receiver, the quality of signal reception is mainly dictated by its Bit Error Rate (BER) and for an analog receiver, the quality of signal reception is mainly dictated by Signal to Noise Ratio (SNR) at the demodulator's input. Hence, to maintain the certain quality of reception by a receiver (either analog or digital) over its wide Input Dynamic Range (IDR), the carrier level at demodulator input should remain constant. An AGC amplifier in a receiver serves this purpose. An AGC amplifier is usually used in the RF front end of a radio receiving system so that the carrier power level at the demodulator input remains almost constant in spite of the changing drive level at the receiver's input. Thus, an AGC amplifier provides a wide Input Dynamic Range (IDR) to a radio reception system. In this paper, an analytical method has been presented to estimate the noise figure of AGC amplifier of the following two types:

Type-1: A Single-Stage AGC Amplifier

Type-2: A Double-Stage AGC Amplifier

The practical method adopted here for measuring the noise figure of an AGC amplifier requires a signal generator and a spectrum analyzer. Using this method, the noise figure of a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier is measured over a wide range of input drive level. The measured noise figure values at different input drive levels are then compared with the estimated values computed by analytical method.

A single-stage AGC amplifier is a cascade of one Voltage Variable Attenuator (VVA) unit and one Fixed Gain Amplifier (FGA) unit, where the VVA unit is placed in front of the FGA unit as shown in Figure 1(a). A dual-stage AGC amplifier is a cascade of two Voltage Variable Attenuator (VVA) units and two Fixed Gain Amplifiers (FGA) units, where the VVA units are placed in front of the FGA units as shown in Figure 1(b).

The IDR (also called the AGC range) of an AGC amplifier is numerically equal to the range of attenuation of the VVA unit. Higher the range of attenuation, wider will be the IDR. On the other hand, the maximum output power of an AGC amplifier over its IDR is proportional to the gain of the FGA unit. Higher the gain of the FGA unit, higher will be output power from the AGC amplifier.

The placement of the VVA unit in front of the FGA unit may increase the noise figure (in dB) of the cascade by an amount equal to the attenuation value (in dB) of the VVA unit. However, to get higher power handling capacity of a radio receiver (i.e., to get the higher operating point input power), usually the VVA unit will be preceded by the FGA unit as shown in Figures 1(a) and 1(b).

Figure 1. Basic block diagram of AGC Amplifier

ESTIMATION OF NOISE FIGURE OF AN AGC AMPLIFIER: THE WORKING PRINCIPLE

Let us define the following parameters:

C_{in}	=	Carrier power at the AGC amplifier input (in mW)
N_{in}	=	Noise power at the AGC amplifier input (in mW)
C_{out}	=	Carrier power at the AGC amplifier output (in mW)
N_{out}	=	Noise power at the AGC amplifier output (in mW)
$(N_o)_{in}$	=	Noise power density at the AGC amplifier input (in mW/Hz)
$(N_o)_{out}$	=	Noise power density at the AGC amplifier output (in mW/Hz)
P_{in}	=	Carrier or signal power at the AGC amplifier input (in dBm)
P_{out}	=	Carrier or signal power at the AGC amplifier output (in dBm)
$(n_o)_{in}$	=	Noise power density at the AGC amplifier input (in dBm/Hz)
$(n_o)_{out}$	=	Noise power density at the AGC amplifier output (in dBm/Hz)

Estimation of Noise figure for a 70 MHz Single-Stage AGC Amplifier

Let us define the following parameters:

F_s	=	Noise Figure of the single-stage AGC amplifier (in dB)
A	=	Instantaneous attenuation value (in dB) of the VVA unit
F_o	=	Noise figure of the FGA unit
G_o	=	Gain of the FGA unit (in dB)
G	=	Instantaneous gain of the AGC amplifier (in dB)

A single-stage AGC amplifier (as shown in Figure 1(a)) is the cascade of a VVA unit and an FGA unit. Hence, using Friis' formula [1-5], one could say that its noise figure will be equal to the noise figure of the FGA unit plus the attenuation value of the VVA unit. Consequently, the noise figure, F_s (in dB) of a single stage AGC amplifier could be expressed analytically by the following expression:

$$F_s(\text{dB}) = A + F_o \quad (1.1)$$

For an AGC amplifier, the total instantaneous attenuation, A is related to the instantaneous gain, G by the following equation,

$$A = G_o - G \quad (1.2)$$

$$F_s = F_o + G_o - G \quad (1.3)$$

For example, if the single-stage AGC amplifier (as shown in Figure 1(a)) is made of Mini-Circuit make MAR-8A+ Fixed Gain Amplifier (FGA), from the datasheet [6] of the FGA unit, one could get, its gain, $G_o \approx 31 \text{ dB}$ and its noise figure, $F_o \approx 2 \text{ dB}$.

$$\text{Hence, } F_s = 33 - G \quad (1.4)$$

From the measured gain characteristic of the AGC amplifier, the instantaneous gain, G will be known. Consequently, the noise figure, F_s of the AGC amplifier at different input levels could be estimated using Equation (1.4).

Estimation of Noise figure for a 70 MHz Double-Stage AGC Amplifier

Let us define the following parameters:

g_1	=	Gain of the FGA-1 unit (as a ratio, not in dB)
g_2	=	Gain of the FGA-2 unit (as a ratio, not in dB)
f_1	=	Noise figure of the FGA-1 unit (as a ratio, not in dB)
f_2	=	Noise figure of the FGA-2 unit (as a ratio, not in dB)
a_1	=	Instantaneous attenuation value of the VVA-1 unit (as a ratio, not in dB)
a_2	=	Instantaneous attenuation value of the VVA-2 unit (as a ratio, not in dB)
f_d	=	Noise factor of the Dual-Stage AGC Amplifier (as a ratio)
G_1	=	Gain of the FGA-1 unit (in dB)
G_2	=	Gain of the FGA-2 unit (in dB)
F_1	=	Noise figure of the FGA-1 unit (in dB)
F_2	=	Noise figure of the FGA-2 unit (in dB)
A_1	=	Instantaneous attenuation value of the VVA-1 unit alone (in dB)
A_2	=	Instantaneous attenuation value of the VVA-2 unit alone (in dB)
A_{01}	=	Residual attenuation or insertion loss of the VVA-1 unit (in dB)
A_{02}	=	Residual attenuation or insertion loss of the VVA-2 unit (in dB)
A	=	Total instantaneous attenuation value (in dB) due to VVA-1 and VVA-2 units combined together
F_d	=	Noise figure of the Dual-Stage AGC Amplifier (in dB)

Using Friis' formula, the noise factor, f_d of a Dual-Stage AGC Amplifier could be expressed as Follows:

$$f_d = a_1 + a_1(f_1 - 1) + \frac{a_1(a_2 - 1)}{g_1} + \frac{a_1 a_2 (f_2 - 1)}{g_1} \quad (2.1)$$

After simplification, Equation (2.1) could be expressed as follows:

$$f_d = a_1 f_1 + \frac{a_1}{g_1} (a_2 f_2 - 1) \quad (2.2)$$

Since, $A_1 = 10\text{Log}_{10}(a_1)$, $A_2 = 10\text{Log}_{10}(a_2)$,

$F_1 = 10\text{Log}_{10}(f_1)$, $F_2 = 10\text{Log}_{10}(f_2)$ and

$G_1 = 10\text{Log}_{10}(g_1)$,

Equation (2.2) could be expressed in the following form:

$$f_d = 10^{(A_1 + F_1)/10} + 10^{(A_1 - G_1)/10} \{10^{(A_2 + F_2)/10} - 1\} \quad (2.3)$$

The Instantaneous attenuation value, A (in dB) of the VVA-1 and VVA-2 units combined together could be expressed as follows:

$$A = A_1 + A_2$$

Since, for the dual-stage AGC amplifier, the control voltage (corresponding to a certain carrier or signal input power, P_{in}) is the same, the instantaneous attenuations, A_1 and A_2 will be equal *i.e.*,

$$A_1 = A_2 = \frac{A}{2} \quad (2.4)$$

For an AGC amplifier, the total instantaneous attenuation, A is related to the instantaneous gain, G by the following equation,

$$A = G_1 + G_2 - G \quad (2.5)$$

Combining Equations (2.4) and (2.5),

$$A_1 = A_2 = 0.5(G_1 + G_2 - G) \quad (2.6)$$

For the 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier (which was designed, developed and fabricated in-house), the FGA-1 and FGA-2 units are of Mini Circuits make with model MAR-8A+. On the other hand, the VVA-1 and VVA-2 units are of Analog Devices make with model HMC346C8.

From the datasheet [6] of fixed gain amplifiers, FGA-1 and FGA-2 (each of model, MAR-8A+ and of Mini-Circuits make),

$$F_1 = F_2 \approx 2 \text{ dB}$$

$$G_1 = G_2 \approx 31 \text{ dB}$$

Hence, $A_1 = A_2 = 0.5(62 - G) = 31 - 0.5G$

Also,

$$(A_1 + F_1) = 33 - 0.5G, (A_1 - G_1) = -0.5G \quad \text{and} \quad (A_2 + F_2) = 33 - 0.5G$$

Consequently, from Equation (2.3), the noise factor, f_d could be expressed in the following form:

$$f_d = 10^{(3.3-0.05G)} + 10^{(-0.05G)}\{10^{(3.3-0.05G)} - 1\} \quad (2.7)$$

Hence, the noise figure, F_d (in dB) of the dual stage AGC amplifier could now be expressed as

$$F_d = 10\log_{10}(f_d) \quad (2.8)$$

Substituting f_d from Equation (2.7) into Equation (2.8),

$$F_d = 10 \log_{10} [10^{(3.3-0.05G)} + 10^{(-0.05G)} \{10^{(3.3-0.05G)} - 1\}] \quad (2.9)$$

Equation (2.9) could be used to estimate noise figure, F_d once the gain of the amplifier is known.

EXPERIMENTAL MEASUREMENTS ON AN AGC AMPLIFIER RELATED TO NOISE

Noise Figure Measurement of a 70 MHz Dual-Stage AGC Amplifier

Basic Principle:

For a receiving system, the noise factor (f) is defined as the ratio of the carrier to noise ratio at its input to the carrier to noise ratio at its output.

From the definition, the Noise Factor, f of the AGC amplifier will be given by

$$f = \frac{\left(\frac{C_{in}}{N_{in}}\right)}{\left(\frac{C_{out}}{N_{out}}\right)} \quad (3.1)$$

If the carrier power and the noise power measurements are carried out on a Spectrum Analyzer over a certain Resolution Bandwidth (RBW), the Equation (3.1) could be expressed in the following form:

$$f = \frac{\left[\frac{C_{in}}{(N_o)_{in}}\right]}{\left[\frac{C_{out}}{(N_o)_{out}}\right]} \quad (3.2)$$

The Noise factor (f), when expressed in dB is called Noise Figure (F). This means the noise figure,

$$F(\text{dB}) = 10 \log_{10}(f) \quad (3.3)$$

Substituting, f from Equation (3.2) in Equation (3.3), one could write,

$$F(\text{dB}) = 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{C_{in}}{(N_o)_{in}} \right] - 10 \log_{10} \left[\frac{C_{out}}{(N_o)_{out}} \right] \quad (3.4)$$

After simplification, the Equation (3.4) could be re-written as

$$F(\text{dB}) = -(n_o)_{in} - (P_{out} - P_{in}) + (n_o)_{out} \quad (3.5)$$

When the AGC amplifier input is connected to signal generator, the noise power density at its input is mainly due to the thermal noise at ambient, which is equal to -174 dBm/Hz. Consequently, one could write,

$$(n_o)_{in} = -174$$

Also, the second term, $(P_{out} - P_{in})$ of Equation (3.5) represents the instantaneous gain, G (in dB) of the AGC amplifier. Hence, from Equation (3.5), the noise figure of the FGA unit could be expressed as follows:

$$F(\text{dB}) = 174 - G + (n_o)_{out} \quad (3.6)$$

During input / output characteristic measurement of an AGC amplifier, the instantaneous gain, G (in dB) and the noise power density, $(n_o)_{out}$ (in dBm/Hz) at its output over its IDR (or beyond) could be measured accurately. Consequently, the noise figure of the AGC amplifier could be computed offline using Equation (3.6). The technique described here is known as **Gain method or Cold source method** of noise figure measurement [7-10].

Measurement Test Set-up

The block schematic of the noise figure measurement set-up for a 70 MHz Dual-Stage AGC amplifier using gain method is shown in the Figure 2. The test set-up mainly consists of a signal generator and a Spectrum Analyzer.

Figure 2. Noise figure measurement set-up for a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier using gain method

Measurement Procedures

The RF output port of the signal generator is connected at the input port of the AGC amplifier as shown in the figure. The AGC amplifier's output port is connected to a Spectrum Analyzer. The following steps could then be followed to measure the noise figure of the transponder:

Step-1: Connect the DC supply (+5V, -5V and ground) to the AGC amplifier. Set the Spectrum Analyzer with centre frequency of 70 MHz, Span of 1 MHz, Resolution Bandwidth of 30 KHz and Video Bandwidth of 100 Hz.

Step-2: Switch ON the AGC amplifier. Check its noise floor on Spectrum Analyzer. Also check the DC current drawn on the power supply display.

Step-3: Set the frequency on the signal generator as 70 MHz, the operating frequency of the AGC amplifier. Set the power level on the signal generator to such a value so that the power input to the AGC amplifier is equal to -80 dBm.

Step-4: For -80 dBm input, measure the output power on the Spectrum Analyzer and also the output noise power density (using Marker function). Compute the gain for this input power and then compute the noise figure using the Equation (3.6). This computed value of noise figure is its measured value corresponding to the input power of -89 dBm

Step-5: Go on increasing the signal generator level at 5 dB step so that the power input to the AGC amplifier also increases at 5 dB step. At each step of the input power, measure the output power, measure the output noise power density, compute the gain and then compute the noise figure using the Equation (3.6). These computed values of noise figure will be the measured values of noise figure corresponding to the different input levels. Go on increasing the input power up to the upper limit of its AGC range, where the output power just starts decreasing.

Step-6: Plot the noise figure values measured in this way against the input power level. This will represent the noise figure characteristic of the AGC amplifier at 70 MHz.

Carrier to Noise Density Ratio (CNDR) Measurement of a 70 MHz Dual-Stage AGC Amplifier

The experimental data obtained during noise figure measurement (as shown in Table 1 for 70 MHz dual-stage AGC amplifier) could be used to compute offline the CNDR value at the output of an AGC amplifier using the following equation:

$$(CNDR)_{out} = C_{in} - (n_o)_{out} \quad (3.7)$$

Where, $(CNDR)_{out}$ = Carrier to Noise Density Ratio at the amplifier's output

The computed results of $(CNDR)_{out}$ corresponding to different input power levels will represent the measured output CNDR characteristic of the AGC amplifier.

COMPARISON OF RESULTS:

Measured vs Estimated

The Table 1 shows the measured values of noise figures of a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier obtained by the cold-source method or gain method as described in previous section. The instantaneous gain (G) values and the output noise density $[(n_o)_{out}]$ values obtained during input/output measurement are used to compute the noise figure using Equation (3.6).

The Equation (2.9) represents the analytical method to estimate the noise figure of an AGC amplifier. It is to be noted that to estimate the noise figure value, the Equation (2.9) only requires the instantaneous gain (G) value of the AGC amplifier. Figure 3 shows the measured input/output characteristic curve obtained using the data as shown in Table 1. The estimated values of noise figure obtained using Equation (2.9) are also shown in the right most column of Table 1. A comparison between the estimated values and the measured values is shown graphically in Figure 4.

Figure 4 indicates that there is a closed match between the measured values and the estimated values of noise figure. This means, the Equation (2.9) provides an easier alternative method of noise figure measurement, where one does not require the measured values of gain and output noise density unlike gain method but requires only the measured values of gain. In other words, one could say that the alternative method (the use of Equation (2.9)) could be used to measure the noise figure of an AGC amplifier just by measuring its input/output characteristic only.

Table 1: Measured and Estimated values of noise figure of a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier

Input power in dBm	Output power in dBm	Measured Gain in dB	Output Noise density at the in dBm/Hz	Measured Noise figure in dB	Estimated values of Noise figure in dB
-80	-22.6	57.4	-112.9	3.7	4.3
-75	-17	58	-112.9	3.1	4
-70	-12.6	57.4	-112.9	3.7	4.3
-65	-7	58	-112.9	3.1	4
-60	-2.7	57.3	-112.9	3.8	4.3
-55	2.5	57.5	-112.9	3.6	4.3
-50	2.5	52.5	-115.8	5.8	6.8
-45	2.6	47.6	-118.4	8	9.2
-40	2.7	42.7	-120.7	10.6	11.7
-35	2.8	37.8	-123	13.3	14.2
-30	2.8	32.8	-125.3	16	16.7
-25	2.7	27.7	-127.3	19	19.3
-20	2.7	22.7	-129.4	21.9	22
-15	2.6	17.6	-130.5	25.9	24.7
-10	2.6	12.6	-132.5	28.9	27.6

Figure 3. Input/output characteristic of a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier

Figure 4. Comparison of noise figure characteristics of a 70 MHz double-stage AGC amplifier

Using the noise figure measurement data (as shown in Table 1), the CNDR values at the AGC amplifier's output, computed using Equation (3.7) represent the measured values of CNDR at its output. For a 70 MHz dual-stage AGC amplifier, the measured values of noise power density, $(n_o)_{out}$ at the amplifier's output are plotted in Figure 5. Consequently, the measured values of $(CNDR)_{out}$ are shown graphically in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Output noise power density vs input power of a 70 MHz dual-stage AGC amplifier

Figure 6. Carrier to Noise Density Ratio (CNDR) at the output vs input power of a 70 MHz dual-stage AGC amplifier

OBSERVATIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

From the measured and estimated results as presented in previous section, the following points could be derived:

- (1) The noise figure of an AGC amplifier remains constant when it operates below its AGC threshold. This constant value of noise figure is almost equal to the sum of the residual attenuation (or insertion loss) of the VVA unit and the noise figure of the FGA unit in the first stage. Within the AGC range, the noise figure increases with input power level and the slope of the noise figure characteristic is almost equal to 0.5 dB/1 dB. In linear scale, it indicates that the noise factor is proportional to the square root of input power when the amplifier operates within its AGC range.
- (2) The noise density at the AGC amplifier's output remains constant when it operates below its AGC threshold. Within the AGC range, the noise density decreases with input power level and the slope of the noise figure characteristic is almost equal to - 0.5 dB/1 dB. In linear scale, it indicates

that the output noise density is inversely proportional to the square root of input power when the amplifier operates within its AGC range.

(3) When the AGC amplifier operates below its AGC threshold, it works like a fixed gain amplifier, where, the output CNDR increases linearly with input power and the slope of the output CNDR characteristic is equal to 1 dB/1dB. Within the AGC range, the noise output CNDR increases with input power and the slope of the output CNDR characteristic is almost equal to equal to 0.5 dB/1dB. In linear scale, it indicates that the output CNDR is proportional to the square root of input power when the amplifier operates within its AGC range.

The analysis and estimation of the noise figure presented in the paper could be used for design and simulation of the AGC amplifiers (of both the single-stage and double-stage types) at different frequencies for various operations. The analytical method presented in the paper could be used as mathematical tool for the AGC amplifier's designers.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are thankful to Shri V. Krishnan, Group Director, Spacecraft Checkout Group and Shri Ramanagouda V Nadagouda, the Deputy Director, ICA, for their constant encouragement and motivation for writing this paper. The authors are also thankful to their other colleagues in Spacecraft Checkout Group (SCG) who have provided the required technical inputs while writing the paper.

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